

WORD PLAY AS A STYLISTIC TOOL AND WAYS TO TRANSLATE FROM ENGLISH TO OTHER LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article discusses the methods of translation and the phenomenon of word games that occur in the process of translation and in language in general. At the same time, the importance of word play as a stylistic tool. And in the process of translating from one language to another, the specifics of the words encountered in this phenomenon are considered.

Key words: pun, play on words, language form, author's style, literal translation
In linguistics, the translation of a text from a foreign language into Russian is one of the most effective real ways of exchanging scientific, literary, aesthetic, philosophical and cultural values of the peoples of different countries and continents. In linguistics, there is still no common understanding of the essence of a pun, which is also reflected in the terminological inconsistency. This technique is often called "word play", "verbal witticism", "double sense", etc. Below are definitions of a pun taken from various sources.

A pun (fr. calembour) is a play on words based on deliberate or involuntary ambiguity generated by homonymy or similarity in sound and causing a comic effect. A pun is a joke based on the comical use of words that sound similar but have different meanings. A pun (English, French calembour) is a figure of speech consisting in a humorous (parodic) use of different meanings of the same word or two similar-sounding words. A pun is a witty joke based on the use of words similar in sound, but different by meaning, or by using different meanings of the same word; play on words. The meaning of the pun lies in the striking contrast between the meaning of the same-sounding words. At the same time, in order to impress, the pun must be new, it must strike with an as yet unknown juxtaposition of words.

A pun is not only a sound game, but also a subtle observation or teaching, it expresses a hint, assessment, mockery or irony, carries a secret meaning. In other words, it is a unity of form and content; the absence of either of these two components destroys the pun. Given the modern meaning of a pun as a figure of speech with a certain stylistic orientation, one could consider puns "random", but the author deliberately made them random, reproducing an end-to-end pun that reveals a way of thinking, habitual speech, one or another feature of the

character. Thus, thanks to a pun, the author can describe the appearance of the hero, his character or mental state. Being skillfully used, the pun is an adornment of any work, but at the same time a serious test for the translator. Unlike the translation of an ordinary text, in which its content (including images, connotations, background, author's style) needs to be poured into a new language form, when translating a pun, the phonetic and/or graphic form of the original is also subject to reexpression. Moreover, it is often necessary even to change the content to a new one if it is impossible to keep the old one, since the plan of expression may be more important than the plan of content. It is relatively rare to achieve a correct translation without changing the form, since between the used words (phraseological units) of a foreign language and the correlative units of the target language, there should be not just equivalent relations, but complete equivalence covering two or more meanings. However, even in this situation, one cannot always count on a 100% successful translation: between equivalents, discrepancies that are imperceptible under other circumstances are often quite unexpectedly found - in compatibility, frequency or usage, in stylistic coloring or emotional charge, in a set of synonyms or antonyms, in etymology or word-formation possibilities. And sometimes even a seemingly insignificant difference is enough to prevent the correct reproduction of the pun in the target language and force the translator to look for new ways for this. basis, the content of the reception is conveyed in a non-punning form. The main techniques for translating a pun are: omission, compensation and tracing. When accepting omission, the pun is omitted completely, the transfer of text into another language is carried out by simple translation. Of course, the transfer of a pun in a non-punning form entails certain losses. However, the translator has a reliable means of compensation in his arsenal - the reception of compensation, one of the ways to achieve translation equivalence at the level of the entire text. Compensation is considered as the replacement of an unfaithful element of the original with a similar or other element that compensates for the loss of information and is capable of having a similar (similar) effect on the reader. Tracing is the construction of lexical units on the model of the corresponding words of a foreign language by accurately translating their significant parts or borrowing individual meanings of words. To enhance compensatory or puns created on a modified semantic basis, translators use two types of graphic means: a) font highlights; b) capital letters. Using this technique, the elements of the core of the pun stand out against the background of the rest of the text, which draws the attention of readers to the content of the technique

and facilitates its decoding. Most often, graphic enhancement is used in works for children. In cases where translators are given creative freedom, this freedom is always formally conditioned and limited by the features of the original. Ignoring them often leads to gross errors on the part of translators. Often, when using a pun, comic situations are created that are far from clear to everyone, since a thin line of humor is conveyed with the help of a play on words. Humor is different, and humor using a play on words can be classified as intellectual. This is the difficulty in translating a play on words from English into Russian. Difficulties can arise in the most unexpected places, even when translating the simplest words. Translation of a pun cannot be literal, verbatim. The play on words carries the author's intention, so the translator is obliged to preserve it, resorting to any tricks and methods, up to writing his own pun. The translator must decide what is more important in this or that case to convey the content, refusing to play on words or to keep the pun, replacing the image, deviating from the exact meaning of the original text. The appearance of new translations of the same work is a justified and natural phenomenon. The analysis of such translations provides rich material, contributes to the study of the system of translation concepts, generalization of the positive experience of the lack of translation theory and practice. Translation of a pun cannot be literal, verbatim. The play on words carries the author's intention, so the translator is obliged to preserve it, resorting to any tricks and methods, up to writing his own pun. The translator must decide what is more important in this or that case to convey the content, refusing to play on words or to keep the pun, replacing the image, deviating from the exact meaning of the original text. The appearance of new translations of the same work is a justified and natural phenomenon. The analysis of such translations provides rich material, contributes to the study of the system of translation concepts, generalization of the positive experience of the lack of translation theory and practice. Translation of a pun cannot be literal, verbatim. The play on words carries the author's intention, so the translator is obliged to preserve it, resorting to any tricks and methods, up to writing his own pun. The translator must decide what is more important in this or that case to convey the content, refusing to play on words or to keep the pun, replacing the image, deviating from the exact meaning of the original text. The appearance of new translations of the same work is a justified and natural phenomenon. The analysis of such translations provides rich material, contributes to the study of the system of translation concepts, generalization of the positive experience of the lack of translation theory and practice. The translator must decide what is

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